

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HEMP PARTICLE-ADDED ACRYLONITRILE-BUTADIENE- STYRENE (ABS) THERMOPLASTIC BIOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the numerical verifications of the experimentally determined dynamic characteristics of neat Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) thermoplastic as well as hemp fiber particle-added ABS possessing three various weight fractions (1%, 5%, and 10%). To this end, significant dynamic modal parameters including natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes have been predicted by performing finite element analyses in Abaqus engineering software on the rectangular plates with a dimension of 120x145mm whose one edge is clamped and the remaining ones are completely free. Eigenvalue extraction to estimate the first three natural frequencies and the corresponding mode shapes of the rectangular plates has been achieved by using the Lanczos eigensolver which is regarded as one of the most powerful methods for the solution of large generalized eigenvalue problems. The first three natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes have been successfully extracted from the finite element analyses. The predicted dynamic modal parameters have been favorably compared to the modal test measurements. Thus, the experimental results have been validated against the numerical predictions.

Keywords: ABS Biocomposite, Hemp, Finite element analysis, Natural frequency, Mode shape.

INTRODUCTION

Polymers have been extensively utilized in various industries due to their low cost, versatility, and easy processing. Among them, industrially important Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) copolymer is widely used owing to its exceptional mechanical properties such as high impact resistance, stiffness, toughness, and good dimensional stability[1–3]. The concentration and arrangement of monomers in the ABS polymer chain greatly influence its properties. The addition of particulate fillers into the material has also gained prominence in the literature and

industry as a widely used technique to tailor the material properties according to the desired application[4–10]. However, the environmental damage caused by the waste of ABS and other synthetic chemical materials has become a significant issue in today's world, resulting in the development of more sustainable alternatives such as biodegradable polymers and natural fiber-reinforced composites[1,11–17].

Modal parameters play a crucial role in industrial applications, especially in determining the dynamic properties of materials. The natural frequency, damping ratio, and mode shapes are essential in the design and analysis of structures to ensure their performance and reliability. Modal analysis is an effective method to determine these dynamic parameters, and it is widely used in the characterization of polymer materials, including ABS plates[18–20].

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is a powerful tool to predict the dynamic behavior of materials and structures, and it has been extensively utilized in the investigation of ABS and polymer materials[21–24]. The objective of this study is to numerically predict the dynamic characteristics of newly developed environmentally friendly and sustainable hemp particle-reinforced ABS biocomposite plates, which are intended to replace traditional synthetic polymers. To this end, FEA was conducted using ABAQUS software to predict the first three natural frequencies and mode shapes of neat ABS and 1%, 5%, and 10% hemp fiber added ABS plates. The Lanczos method was employed to extract the natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes from the FEA results which is very convenient algorithm to solve eigenvector problems of modal parameters. The Lanczos method has gained widespread utilization in both academic research and industrial application areas due to its remarkable effectiveness in handling large and sparse generalized eigenvalue problems[25–27]. The comparison of experimental and numerical results of the natural frequencies and mode shapes of ABS and hemp fiber added ABS plates is essential to evaluate the accuracy of the FEA predictions. The obtained results are expected to provide valuable insights for the design and analysis of polymer materials and structures.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Finite Element Modeling

In order to estimate the first three natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes numerical simulations were performed using the ABAQUS finite element engineering code. The selection of the most suitable element formulation for the numerical simulations of modal analysis was 4-node reduced integration shell element type, designated S4R, based on several factors (Figure 8). The S4R shell element formulation was chosen for its ability to provide accurate results with less computational time compared to other shell elements. The reduced integration in the S4R element reduces the number of integration points, which leads to a faster computation time while still providing accurate results. Furthermore, the S4R element takes into account transverse shear deformation and can handle thick shell elements, which is important for accurately modeling the plate specimens used in the study[28,29].

Figure 8. S4R element type

To ensure a robust and accurate mesh, the Hypermesh pre-processor software was used to generate identical finite element models of the plate specimens. Hypermesh is a well-established software tool that can accurately mesh complex models with high accuracy. The mesh was composed of 480 S4R shell elements and 525 nodes, with 5 integration points throughout the thickness of the plate specimens. A clamped boundary condition was enforced on one edge of the rectangular specimens through an encastre boundary condition to closely resemble the experimental setup, as depicted in Figure 9. This boundary condition was essential for accurately modeling the plate specimens and obtaining accurate modal analysis results.

Figure 9. Finite element model of plate specimens in ABAQUS

Lanczos Method

The equation of motion for plate can be written in terms of discrete system, thus eigenvalue problem for natural modes finite element model of free vibration in classical notation can be written as:

$$(\mu^2[M] + \mu[C] + [K])\{\phi\} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $[M]$, $[C]$ and $[K]$ are mass, damping and the stiffness matrices respectively, μ is the eigenvalue and $\{\phi\}$ is the eigenvector. In general, the eigensystem stated in Eq.1 will have complex eigenvalues and eigenvectors. By assuming that $[K]$ is symmetric and ignoring $[C]$ during eigenvalue extraction, this problem can be considered symmetric. Generally, $[K]$ will be assumed that is positive semidefinite for symmetric eigenproblems. In this instance, where

μ is the circular frequency, turns into an imaginary eigenvalue $\mu = i\omega$, the eigenvalue problem can be expressed as follows:

$$(-\omega^2[M] + [K])\{\phi\} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The Lanczos eigensolver, one of the most used methods, is utilized in ABAQUS/Standard to extract the natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes of this symmetrized eigenproblem (Eq. 2). The calculation process in ABAQUS/Standard comprises of a number of Lanczos "runs" in which a number of stages are carried out iteratively. The following spectral transformation is used for each Lanczos run:

$$[M]([K] - \sigma[M])^{-1}[M]\{\phi\} = \theta[M]\{\phi\} \quad (3)$$

where σ is the shift, θ is the eigenvalue, and $\{\phi\}$ is the eigenvector. Rapid convergence to the desired eigenvalues is achieved by this modification. The original problem's eigenvalues and the transformed problem's eigenvalues are related in the following ways, while the eigenvectors of the symmetrized problem Eq2 and the transformed problem Eq3 are identical.

$$\omega^2 = \frac{1}{\theta} + \sigma \quad (4)$$

This iterative process that involves the computation of a sequence of orthogonal vectors that span a Krylov subspace. This subspace is used to construct an approximate eigenvector of the original matrix. The Lanczos method is particularly suitable for computing a few eigenvalues (ten in general) and corresponding eigenvectors of large sparse symmetric matrices which is adequate for most engineering applications.

After performing Lanczos steps, each Lanczos run starts with a construction of the shifted matrix $[K] - \sigma_p[M]$ (where p is the run number) [30].

Every block Lanczos step i is utilized in ABAQUS in the following sequence:

- Use the parametric shifted matrix to solve the system of linear equations with b right-hand sides (b is the Lanczos block size):

$$([K] - \sigma_p[M])[\hat{V}]_{i+1} = [M][V]_i \quad (5)$$

where $[V]_i$ is a block of Lanczos vectors. The number of columns of $[V]_i$ represents the block size b while the number of rows represents the number of variables in the finite element model.

A number of random vectors orthonormalized using the method constitute the $[V]_1$ initial block of vectors:

$$[I] = [V]_1^T [M] [V]_1 \quad \text{where } [I] \text{ is the identity matrix.}$$

- Construct the supplemental vector block:

$$[U]_{i+1} = [\hat{V}]_{i+1} - [V]_{i-1}\beta_i \quad (6)$$

where β_i is a $b \times b$ upper triangular matrix. $\beta_1 = [0]$.

- Calculate the symmetric matrix α_i of size b :

$$\alpha_i = [U]_{i+1}^T [M] [V]_i \quad (7)$$

- Generate the Lanczos residual:

$$[R]_{i+1} = [U]_{i+1} - [V]_i \alpha_i \quad (8)$$

- Normalize the residual. Calculate a group of vectors, $[V]_{i+1}$:

$$[V]_{i+1} \beta_{i+1} = [R]_{i+1} \quad (9)$$

and

$$[I] = [V]_{i+1}^T [M] [V]_{i+1} \quad (10)$$

where β_{i+1} is a $b \times b$ upper triangular matrix.

- Utilizing partial reorthogonalization technique, predict the loss of orthogonality between $[V]_{i+1}$ and $[V]_j$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, i - 1$ and if necessary, perform reorthogonalization.
- Local reorthogonalization" is carried out by recalculating $[V]_{i+1}$ to obtain:

$$[0] = [V]_{i+1}^T [M] [V]_i \quad (11)$$

- Compute the simplified eigenvalue problem by treating the band matrix $[T]$ as follows:

$$[T][S] = [S][\theta] \quad (12)$$

where

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & \beta_2^T & & & & \\ \beta_2 & \alpha_2 & \beta_3^T & & & \\ & \beta_3 & \alpha_3 & \dots & & \\ & & \dots & \dots & \beta_i^T & \\ & & & \beta_i & \alpha_i & \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

and $[S]$ and $[\theta]$ are the matrices that contain the reduced eigenproblem's eigenvectors and eigenvalues respectively. The resolution of this issue has been effectively addressed through the application of both the Householder root-finding algorithm and Q-R eigenvalue algorithm.

The material properties required for finite element modal analysis of neat and hemp biocomposite plates, such as elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio, and density, are presented in Table 1.

Table 3. The material specifications implemented in FEA for modal analysis.

Code	Elastic Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Density (tonne/mm ³)
Neat ABS	2191	0.35	1040e-12
Hemp-1	2272	0.35	1040e-12
Hemp-5	2310	0.35	1040e-12
Hemp-10	2370	0.35	1040e-12

RESULTS

Predicted first three natural frequencies of neat and hemp fiber added ABS biocomposite plate specimens, utilizing ABAQUS FEA software with Lanczos method, were tabulated in Table 4. Additionally, mode shapes of specimens with the help of Lanczos method corresponding to these mode frequencies were also numerically estimated in ABAQUS. Numerically derived first three mode shapes were depicted in Figure 10 comparably with the experimentally obtained mode shapes.

Table 4. Natural frequencies of neat and hemp biocomposite plates from FEA.

	Natural Frequencies (Hz)		
	Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3
Neat ABS	68.365	141.49	368.74
Hemp-1	69.617	144.08	375.50
Hemp-5	70.197	145.28	378.62
Hemp-10	71.103	147.16	383.51

Figure 10. First three mode shape comparison of experimental and FEA results for plate specimens.

Figure 10 makes it abundantly evident that the inclusion of hemp fibers enhances the neat ABS material's stiffness, which in turn causes a rise in the natural frequencies of biocomposite

materials. Table 2 shows that at higher frequencies, this difference between natural frequencies becomes more prominent. Although it has been shown that adding hemp fibers increases the natural frequencies of neat ABS, it has also been found that as the amount of hemp fiber addition increases, the increase in natural frequencies actually reduces.

By examining the mode shapes, it is evident that the numerical analysis findings are in a good agreement with the results obtained from the experimental modal analysis. After examining the mode shapes in both experimental and numerical results, it can be concluded that the addition of hemp fiber particles to ABS did not cause any change the overall mode shapes. Besides, in terms of mode shapes, the 1st and 3rd mode shapes correspond to the 1st and 2nd bending modes, respectively, while the 2nd mode shape corresponds to the 1st twisting mode.

Table 5. Comparison of experimental natural frequencies with FEA results.

	Natural Frequencies (Hz)								
	Mode 1			Mode 2			Mode 3		
	Exp.	FEA	Error	Exp.	FEA	Error	Exp.	FEA	Error
Neat ABS	68.0	68.4	0.5	142.5	141.5	0.7	387.5	368.7	4.8
Hemp-1	70.5	69.6	1.3	146.0	144.1	1.3	398.5	375.5	5.8
Hemp-5	69.5	70.2	1.0	144.5	145.3	0.5	394.0	378.6	3.9
Hemp-10	68.5	71.1	3.8	143.0	147.2	2.9	390.0	383.5	1.7

Table 3 provides a comparative analysis of the first three natural frequencies of neat ABS and hemp fiber-reinforced biocomposite ABS test specimens, obtained from numerical and experimental results. As can be clearly seen from Table 3, the first three natural frequencies of plate test specimens were accurately predicted by finite element analysis. The maximum error rate between the experimental and numerical results was determined to be up to 5.8%. It was observed that the error rate in the predictions increased with increasing natural frequency for Neat ABS, Hemp-1, and Hemp-5 specimens, while it was decreased for the Hemp-10 specimen. This increase in the error with increasing natural frequency could be attributed to the high strain sensitivity of ABS material properties that causes an increase in the elastic modulus with increasing strain ratio. In addition, it is known that ABS has different tensile and compressive moduli at the same strain ratio due to its amorphous structure. However, in the finite element analysis of plate specimens, the materials were considered as isotropic and the elastic moduli obtained from the tensile tests at the same strain ratio were taken into account. Considering these facts, it can be said that the high hemp content in the Hemp-10 material affects the material's crystal structure, causing it to act more isotropic and leading to a decrease in the strain sensitivity of ABS, resulting in a decrease in prediction error with increasing frequency.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Grid geometry of neat and hemp fiber added ABS plate specimens were modeled in Hypermesh pre-processor software using S4R 4 node reduced integration shell element. First three natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes were numerically predicted in ABAQUS

engineering FEA software utilizing Lanczos eigensolver method. The following conclusions can be drawn from numerical results as:

The first three natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes were accurately predicted implementing finite element analysis. The error rate is mostly due to the use of an isotropic material model in numerical studies, while ABS is actually an amorphous material with a highly strain-rate-dependent mechanical behavior. To obtain more accurate results, a more convenient complex material model should be applied in the numerical code. Furthermore, the error rates in the predictions increased with increasing natural frequencies in the neat ABS, Hemp-1, and Hemp-5 specimens, while it decreased in the Hemp-10 specimen. The main reason for this might be the high hemp content in the Hemp-10 material crystallizes the amorphous structure of the ABS material with the high cellulose content exist in the hemp fibers, causing it to behave more isotropic and resulting in a less susceptible to the strain-rate dependent behavior of ABS at high frequencies, leading to more accurate predictions.

Comparing the biocomposite materials produced with hemp fiber particle addition to neat ABS, it is observed that the fiber particle addition increases the rigidity of the materials and causes an increase in their natural frequencies.

Although the natural frequencies of the materials change with the addition of hemp fiber, the mode shapes of the first three natural frequencies were not affected and were found to be similar.

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